

1 **Transcriptional changes in C9orf72 hexanucleotide repeat expansion induced pluripotent stem**
2 **cells.**

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7 Degenerative diseases of the musculoskeletal system are studied in Drosophila, in mice, and in cell lines
8 in vitro and while each approach has provided important insights into the molecular mechanisms by which
9 genetic variation or mutation like SOD1 mutants in ALS and triplicate expansion in Huntington's disease
10 confer of result in disease, each approach is unable to faithfully replace important transcriptional activity,
11 that which occurs early in disease and in the appropriate cellular milieu provided cell type-specific gene
12 expression. Here we measure total transcription in C9orf72 FTD/ALS human induced pluripotent stem
13 cells and HEK293T engineered to inducibly express arginine peptide repeats that mimic hexanucleotide
14 expansion in C9ORF72-associated disease to discover and describe the most biologically significant gene
15 expression changes associated with musculoskeletal disease resulting from C9orf72 expression. We
16 identified activation of dermokine in cells expressing arginine peptide repeats, and in C9orf72 FTD/ALS
17 induced pluripotent stem cells. Dermokine was co-regulated with ESRP2, a splicing regulator important
18 for mammalian development.
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Results

We studied total transcriptional in induced pluripotent stem cells from patients with C9orf72 FTD/ALS and HEK cells engineered to expression peptide arginine repeats found in C9orf72 FTD/ALS to study transcriptional qualities of degenerative musculoskeletal disease.

Figure 1: Loss of KDM4B in induced pluripotent stem cells from humans with C9orf72 FTD/ALS.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
23030	2.17E-05	0.1193	4.246703	0.5068305	559.52	KDM4B	417/13257	

KDM4B expressed was also reduced in HEK cells expressing peptide arginine repeats.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
23030	2.91E-08	0.0798	5.546854	0.4424453	1187.1	KDM4B	4483/18014	

Figure 2: Activation of ZNF772 and DMKN in C9orf72 FTD/ALS iPS cells and in HEK cells engineered to express peptide arginine repeats.

GSE238005

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
400720	1.22E-03	0.2423	-3.235007	-0.7838863	71.95	ZNF772	1272/	
93099	1.74E-06	0.2298	-4.781321	-1.0985259	158.65	DMKN	217/	

ZNF772 and DMKN transcriptional induction was also observed in peptide arginine repeat-expressing HEK cells.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
400720	1.10E-43	0.1032	-13.860214	-1.4300868	397.42	ZNF772	290/	
93099	3.49E-90	0.0582	-20.13719	-1.172707	2793.18	DMKN	40/	

Figure 3: Modulation of HAPLN3 in C9orf72 FTD/ALS.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
145864	3.38E-11	0.2447	-6.629105	-1.6220878	58.18	HAPLN3	6/	

In peptide arginine repeat-expressing HEK cells, HAPLN3 was also among the most differentially expressed gene transcriptome-wide, but here, it was silenced.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
145864	1.84E-39	0.137	13.144103	1.8003959	271.11	HAPLN3	381/	

Figure 4: Dermokine is co-regulated with ESRP2.

In C9orf72 FTD/ALS iPS, ESRP2 expression was modestly activated.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
80004	3.47E-02	0.0727	-2.111579	-0.1535662	204.21	ESRP2	3574/	

We also observed silencing of the homeobox factor IRX3 in C9orf72 FTD/ALS iPS, concomitant with weak repression of IRX3 in HEK cells expressing peptide arginine repeats.

Figure 5: Repression of IRX3 in C9orf72 FTD/ALS iPS.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
79191	6.23E-12	0.2283	6.874341	1.5692178	312.76	IRX3	4/	

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
79191	7.90E-02	0.1011	1.756285	0.1775236	437.05	IRX3	12060/	

Discussion

We used next generation technologies in conjunction with induced pluripotent stem cells and human cells that recapitulate expression of arginine peptide repeats to study gene expression in C9orf72 FTD/ALS. Dermokine, the splicing regulator ESRP2, hyaluronan-associated genes, and the nuclear factor ZNF772 may be pertinent to transcriptional biology of musculoskeletal degenerative disorders.

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Methods

We measured total transcription in iPS cells and transgenic HEK cells using datasets GSE238005 and GSE193962 in conjunction with R-based computational methods and SEEK.